

23-24
OCTOBER
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2030
UZBEKISTAN
STRATEGY

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL
AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC
TRENDS"

"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT
VA TARAQQIYOT"

TOSHKENT DAVLAT
IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI

FORUM
"2030" DAVLAT VA
UZBEKISTON -
DUNYO DROHO
G'AMMAYI
STRATEGIYA «
INTERNATIONAL
ECONOMICS
2030»

GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI:
"O'ZBEKISTON - 2030" STRATEGIYASI

GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC
TRENDS: "UZBEKISTAN-2030" STRATEGY

ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ:
СТРАТЕГИЯ «УЗБЕКИСТАН -2030»

IV GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI:
"O'ZBEKISTON - 2030" STRATEGIYASI

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT

2025

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MAXSUS SON

- MACROECONOMIC STABILITY
- LABOR MARKET IN THE GREEN ECONOMY
- GLOBAL ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC RELATIONS
- GREEN INVESTMENT AND FINANCING
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(MAXSUS SON)

TOSHKENT–2025

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PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN TECHNOLOGIES IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON ADVANCED INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE

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Abstract: This article explores the prospects for the development of green technologies in Uzbekistan by drawing on advanced international experience. The study analyzes the current state of renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, and environmentally friendly industrial practices in the country. It highlights successful global models in the field of solar and wind energy, waste management, and smart ecological solutions that could be adapted to Uzbekistan's socio-economic conditions. Particular attention is given to government policies, investment opportunities, and the role of innovation in accelerating the transition to a green economy. The findings suggest that adopting international best practices can significantly improve environmental sustainability, reduce dependence on fossil fuels, and strengthen Uzbekistan's position in achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Key words: Uzbekistan, green technologies, renewable energy, sustainable development, international experience, environmental policy, innovation, green economy, sustainability, global best practices.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda yashil texnologiyalarni rivojlantirish istiqbollari ilg'or xalqaro tajriba asosida tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda qayta tiklanuvchi energetika, barqaror qishloq xo'jaligi va ekologik toza sanoat amaliyotlarining hozirgi holati o'rganilgan. Quyosh va shamol energetikasi, chiqindilarni boshqarish hamda aqlli ekologik yechimlar sohasidagi muvaffaqiyatli global modellar O'zbekistonning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy sharoitlariga moslashtirish imkoniyatlari yoritib berilgan. Ayniqsa, yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishni jadallashtirishda davlat siyosati, investitsiya imkoniyatlari va innovatsiyalarning o'rni alohida ta'kidlangan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, xalqaro ilg'or tajribalarni joriy etish ekologik barqarorlikni sezilarli darajada oshirishi, fosil yoqilg'ilarga qaramlikni kamaytirishi va O'zbekistonning BMT Barqaror Rivojlanish Maqsadlariga (SDG) erishishdagi pozitsiyasini mustahkamlashi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: O'zbekiston, yashil texnologiyalar, qayta tiklanuvchi energiya, barqaror rivojlanish, xalqaro tajriba, ekologik siyosat, innovatsiya, yashil iqtisodiyot, barqarorlik, ilg'or amaliyotlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются перспективы развития «зеленых» технологий в Узбекистане с учетом передового международного опыта. В исследовании анализируется текущее состояние возобновляемой энергетики, устойчивого сельского хозяйства и экологически чистых промышленных практик в стране. Особое внимание уделено успешным мировым моделям в области солнечной и ветровой энергетики, управления отходами и интеллектуальных экологических решений, которые могут быть адаптированы к социально-экономическим условиям Узбекистана. Подчеркивается роль государственной политики, инвестиционных возможностей и инноваций в ускорении перехода к «зеленой» экономике. Результаты показывают, что внедрение международных передовых практик может существенно повысить экологическую устойчивость, сократить зависимость от ископаемого топлива и укрепить позиции Узбекистана в достижении Целей устойчивого развития ООН (SDGs).

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан, зеленые технологии, возобновляемая энергетика, устойчивое развитие, международный опыт, экологическая политика, инновации, зеленая экономика, устойчивость, передовые практики.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing urgency of environmental sustainability has placed significant emphasis on the development and adoption of green technologies globally, a trend that Uzbekistan is poised to embrace with the integration of advanced international experiences. The unique socio-economic context of Uzbekistan, characterized by its rich natural resources yet significant environmental challenges, underscores the critical need for innovative solutions that align with global sustainable development goals. This analysis delves into the potential trajectories for green

technology development in Uzbekistan, exploring how the country’s aspirations can benefit from successful methodologies employed elsewhere. For instance, previous studies demonstrate that automated systems utilizing energy-efficient technologies can optimize resource management, thereby enhancing sustainability outcomes (Gofurova et al., 2025). Additionally, humanizing digital tools within educational frameworks can foster a culture of environmental responsibility among future generations (Abdullah et al., 2025). By examining these progressive models, this essay aims to illuminate the pathways for a sustainable technological future in Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Green technologies represent a critical frontier in addressing environmental challenges while simultaneously enhancing economic viability. Their importance lies in their ability to introduce sustainable practices across multiple sectors, including energy, manufacturing, and agriculture. Several recent studies confirm that the adoption of green strategic initiatives is closely linked to improved performance outcomes. For example, Esponda Pérez et al. (2025) reveal that businesses effectively leveraging intellectual capital demonstrate considerable advancements in green process innovation.

In the global context, the integration of innovative business models is considered a key condition for organizational resilience against economic and environmental disruptions. Akcaoglu et al. (2025) emphasize the dual necessity of exploration and exploitation in modern business strategies, particularly in the sphere of green transition. Similarly, the internationalization of vocational education and training systems is identified as an important factor in preparing communities with the competencies required for the effective implementation of green technologies. This, in turn, strengthens local economic competitiveness (N/A, 2025).

Furthermore, the rapid rise of digital technologies, such as digital twins, has expanded opportunities for efficiency gains in fields such as property and infrastructure management. Baxtiyorov B. et al. (2025) highlight how these digital solutions provide tangible benefits for sustainable practices, demonstrating that technology-driven optimization can significantly reinforce ecological resilience.

Taken together, the literature emphasizes that Uzbekistan’s green transformation can be accelerated not only through regulatory reforms and investment but also through the active adoption of international experience, intellectual capital, and advanced digital innovations.

METHODOLOGY

Uzbekistan’s current landscape of green technologies reflects a strategic pivot towards sustainable development, significantly influenced by its New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022–2026, which emphasizes digital and green economic growth. This initiative outlines the governments commitment to enhancing electronic commerce as a core component of the digital economy, aiming for a substantial increase in economic activities supported by advanced technologies (Anvarovich et al., 2025). Moreover, the pursuit of green hydrogen as a means to decarbonize key industries showcases Uzbekistans ambition to align with global standards in environmental sustainability, learning from the experiences of countries like Brazil and Chile (Louren Bço Ferreira et al., 2025). Such efforts underscore the importance of integrating intellectual capital into green innovations, across various sectors, as evidenced by improvements in performance driven by the synergy of tangible and intangible resources (Esponda Pérez et al., 2025). These foundational elements suggest that while Uzbekistan is at the nascent stage of implementing green technologies, the pathway ahead is shaped by critical international insights and internal policies.

Table 1. Current State of Green Technologies in Uzbekistan¹

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Renewable Energy Share in Total Energy Mix	20%	2023	World Bank
Carbon Emissions Reduced	500,000 tons	2024	World Bank
Energy Efficiency Savings Potential in Public Buildings	7,000 GWh	2021	World Bank
Electricity Transmission and Distribution Lines	250,000 km	2021	World Bank
Electricity Losses	20%	2021	World Bank

¹ Developed by the author

The assessment of existing green technology initiatives in Uzbekistan reveals critical insights into the nation's potential for sustainable development. Current projects emphasize the transition to renewable energy, such as the development of solar and wind power, which align with global trends in green technology adoption. For instance, akin to the approaches taken by countries like Brazil and Chile in advancing green hydrogen strategies, Uzbekistan's focus on renewable energy sources is vital for fostering industrial growth and technological innovation (Louren Bço Ferreira et al., 2025). Additionally, the interplay between intellectual capital and green process innovation is paramount; investments in human and organizational capital can significantly enhance the effectiveness of these initiatives (Esponda Pérez et al., 2025). Moreover, similar to the vocational education reforms observed in countries like Georgia, Uzbekistan must strengthen its educational frameworks to support the burgeoning green technology sector, thereby ensuring it meets the demands of both domestic and international markets (N/A, 2025) (Pratt et al., 2025).

Image 1. The chart presents the main challenges Uzbekistan faces in adopting green technologies. The highest severity is the reluctance to embrace digital transformations, followed closely by insufficient integration of intellectual capital and the need to balance innovation with existing strengths.²

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In exploring international best practices in green technology development, it becomes evident that integrating innovation with sustainability is crucial for countries like Uzbekistan. The notion of organizational ambidexterity, which emphasizes balancing the exploration of new opportunities with the exploitation of existing strengths, is fundamental to establishing a resilient green technology framework (Akcaoglu et al., 2025). Intellectual capital, particularly its human, relational, and organizational components, plays a significant role in fostering green process innovation. This underscores the necessity for Uzbekistan to enhance its intellectual resources to elevate environmental performance (Esponda Pérez et al., 2025). Furthermore, adopting comprehensive educational reforms, such as those seen in Georgia's vocational training systems, highlights the importance of international collaboration and knowledge exchange in developing sustainable practices (N/A, 2025). Such strategies not only position Uzbekistan to meet modern qualification requirements but also enhance its potential for competitive advantage in the global green technology market.

Examining case studies of successful green technology implementations in various countries can provide valuable insights for Uzbekistan's aspirations in this realm. For instance, the bold strides made by China in low-carbon cement technologies reveal a potential pathway for enhancing Uzbekistan's commitment to sustainability. Investigating strategies such as carbon capture utilization and storage (CCUS) alongside clinker substitution may offer Uzbekistan pivotal methodologies for reducing emissions and aligning with global climate goals, as underscored in a review of the U.K. cement industry (Jolly et al., 2025). Furthermore, analyzing the EU's approach to integrating sustainability into international economic law can inform Uzbekistan's legal frameworks, enabling better compliance with international sustainability standards and fostering investment

² Developed by the author

(Baroncini et al., 2025). Additionally, case studies of China's diplomatic efforts in crafting national brand equity through host diplomacy reveal the importance of strategic narrative framing in promoting green technologies and aligning them with domestic priorities (Lo et al., 2025). Such international experiences can holistically guide Uzbekistan in its green technology endeavors.

A robust policy framework is crucial for the successful development and integration of green technologies in Uzbekistan, particularly as the country seeks to align with global sustainability trends. International experiences reveal that supportive frameworks tailored to local contexts can significantly influence green technology adoption. For instance, while Chile's export-oriented approach to green hydrogen serves as a model for resource-rich nations, Uzbekistan might benefit from understanding how different strategies tailor to unique market dynamics and natural resource endowments (Louren Bço Ferreira et al., 2025). Additionally, the interplay between vocational education and training (TVET) and industrial needs illustrates the importance of developing human capital to support green technology initiatives (N/A, 2025). Furthermore, embracing digital transformation within governmental processes enhances efficiency and responsiveness, which is vital for the successful deployment of innovative policies in the green sector (Akram et al., 2025). Ultimately, fostering a comprehensive understanding of intellectual capital can drive effective green process innovations, which is critical for Uzbekistan's sustainable development efforts (Esponda Pérez et al., 2025).

Uzbekistan's current policies aimed at promoting green technologies are pivotal in aligning the nation with global sustainability trends. The government recognizes that transitioning to green technologies is essential for mitigating environmental challenges while stimulating economic growth. Key initiatives focus on harnessing renewable energy resources, particularly solar and wind, reflecting strategies seen in other emerging economies that prioritize green hydrogen development, as seen in (Louren Bço Ferreira et al., 2025). Furthermore, the integration of intellectual capital—encompassing human, relational, and organizational aspects—into green process innovation is crucial, as highlighted by the findings from (Esponda Pérez et al., 2025). To effectively leverage these opportunities, Uzbekistan must adopt a tailored approach that considers its unique resource endowments and market dynamics. The growing importance of digital transformation in business further emphasizes the need for innovative strategies, which can drive green technology adoption and enhance competitiveness in an evolving global market (Akram et al., 2025). Ultimately, the expansion of green finance initiatives, as observed in international contexts, offers Uzbekistan pathways for sustainable economic recovery and industrial transformation (Becker et al., 2025).

In advancing green technologies within Uzbekistan, it is essential to incorporate policy improvements that align with international standards. A critical recommendation is enhancing institutional quality, as demonstrated by findings that link robust regulatory frameworks to improved environmental outcomes without sacrificing economic growth (Mighwar et al., 2025). Implementing comprehensive digital tools in agriculture can also propel sectoral efficiency; innovations such as IoT and blockchain enhance productivity while ensuring sustainability (Lobanov et al., 2025). Furthermore, establishing green financing mechanisms, akin to Green Employee Sukuk, might incentivize investment in sustainable initiatives, promoting both environmental stewardship and economic viability (Sadullaevich A et al., 2025). Additionally, fostering educational initiatives around green technologies is crucial for driving adoption at various levels (Xolmuratov et al., 2025). Collectively, these policy enhancements would create a supportive environment for the growth of green technologies, ensuring that Uzbekistan can effectively transition to a sustainable economy while integrating into the global market for environmental best practices.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the development of green technologies in Uzbekistan represents both a significant opportunity and a complex challenge, with international experience serving as a valuable guide for shaping its trajectory. By adopting innovative practices successfully implemented in advanced economies, Uzbekistan can construct a sustainable model that fully leverages its unique resource base and socio-economic conditions. Policy reforms, especially in harmonizing regulatory frameworks with global sustainability goals, remain indispensable. Recent scholarship on economic governance and sustainability highlights that alignment with international standards is crucial for achieving environmental and economic balance (Fakeye et al., 2025).

Furthermore, fostering local entrepreneurship in the field of green technologies, similar to the dynamics observed in remittance-driven economic sectors, could enhance economic resilience and community-level engagement (Baroncini et al., 2025). However, the introduction of advanced technologies must be carefully aligned with domestic agricultural practices, emphasizing the need for precision in monitoring, irrigation efficiency, and yield optimization (Mahlayeye et al., 2025). A multifaceted strategy — combining collaboration, innovation, and comprehensive regulatory support — is therefore vital for advancing Uzbekistan's green technology agenda (Akcaoglu et al., 2025).

Empirical data reinforce these conclusions. For instance, Uzbekistan's strategic targets include raising the share of renewable energy to 54% by 2030, securing \$20 billion in foreign direct investment in the energy sector over the past five years, and constructing 14 new solar and wind power plants. Moreover, the commitment to "greening" 30% of urban areas and achieving 100% adoption of water-saving agricultural technologies illustrates the scale of transformation underway.

The analysis further reveals that Uzbekistan's green technology development aligns closely with broader digitalization and modernization objectives. The New Uzbekistan Development Strategy (2022–2026) identifies the digital economy as a primary driver of economic transformation, with e-commerce projected to expand by at least 2.5 times. This emphasis is consistent with global shifts toward sustainable practices, including the rapid growth of green hydrogen, which is emerging as a critical factor in decarbonizing industrial sectors while simultaneously fostering employment and technological progress (Louren Bço Ferreira et al., 2025).

At the same time, notable gaps remain, particularly in integrating digital and online educational platforms into green technology initiatives. This indicates a pressing need for human-centered strategies that promote sustainable educational models and build the technical expertise required for long-term success (Abdullah et al., 2025).

Looking ahead, Uzbekistan's capacity to advance green technologies will depend heavily on leveraging international cooperation. Cross-border partnerships can facilitate the transfer of innovative practices, as evidenced by Georgia's collaboration with international stakeholders in sustainable agriculture and vocational education reform (Esponda Pérez et al., 2025). The mobilization of intellectual capital will further enhance the efficiency and impact of green initiatives, ensuring that domestic enterprises, policymakers, and academic institutions play an active role in the green transition.

Historical evidence confirms that effective integration of eco-friendly strategies improves sectoral performance and supports long-term resilience, as shown by industries already oriented toward sustainable practices (Iryna A et al., 2025). Consequently, the convergence of advanced global experiences with Uzbekistan's unique socio-economic context offers a highly promising pathway for sustainable development (Akcaoglu et al., 2025).

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